

¹H NMR Studies of Telluracyclopentane-dihalides, -dipseudohalides and Tetrahalotelluracyclopentane Anions

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Synthesis of telluracyclopentane-dihalides, -dipseudohalides and tetrahalotelluracyclopentane anions has been accomplished reported by us earlier¹. The present investigation envisages a systematic ¹H nmr study of telluracyclopentane-dihalides, -dipseudohalides and tetraethylammonium, tetraphenylphosphonium-arsonium, stibonium complexes of telluracyclopentane-1,1-diiodide. P and Te centre and presence of I in the coordination sphere affects the chemical shifts in a different way.

Results and Discussion

The ¹H nmr spectral data of telluracyclopentane-dihalides, -dipseudohalides (C₄H₈TeX₂) (X = Cl, Br, I, N₃,

NCS, SeCN) and tetrahalotelluracyclopentane anionic complexes of the type (R₄M)⁺₂ (C₄H₈TeX₂)²⁻ (R = C₂H₅, M = N; R = C₆H₅; M = P, As, Sb; X' = Cl, Br, I) are summarised in Tables 1 and 2. The salient features of the study are presented below.

Telluracyclopentane-dihalides, -dipseudohalides : Telluracyclopentane-1,1-diiodide contains -CH₂-Te- and -CH₂-C- protons which appear as multiplets centered at δ 3.60 and 2.84 respectively. In (C₄H₈TeX₂) (X = Cl, Br, I), the -CH₂-Te- (H') and -CH₂-C- (H') decrease with the decrease in electronegativity of the halides (Table 1) and the plot of their chemical shifts vs x_p of X is linear.

Tetrahalotelluracyclopentane complex anions : In case of tetraethylammonium complexes of C₄H₈TeI₂ (Table 2, sl. nos. 2-4) there is a slight downfield shift of -CH₂-Te- protons and they appear at δ 3.63 ± 0.03 whereas -CH₂-C- protons appear at almost the same position at δ 2.83 ± 0.01. In case of tetraphenylphosphonium complexes there is a slight downfield shift of -CH₂-Te- protons, for complexes having Cl, Br in coordination sphere (δ 3.63 ± 0.04) (sl. nos. 5, 6). But in case of iodine-containing complex (sl. no. 7) there is a high field shift of -CH₂-Te- protons (δ 3.55 ppm).

There is a linear variation of the chemical shifts corresponding to -CH₂-Te- protons, -CH₂-C- protons and Δ** (Table 2) vs electronegativity of the halogen atoms (Cl,

TABLE 1—¹H NMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS (δ) OF TELLURACYCLOPENTANE-DIHALIDES, -DIPSEUDOHALIDES

Sl. no	Compd.	-CH ₂ -Te-(H')	-CH ₂ -C-(H')	Δ**	Electronegativity (x)
1	C ₄ H ₈ TeI ₂	3.60	2.84	0.76	2.52
2	C ₄ H ₈ TeBr ₂	3.78	2.90	0.88	2.62
3	C ₄ H ₈ TeCl ₂	4.02	3.22	0.80	2.95
4	C ₄ H ₈ Te(NCS) ₂	3.33	2.68	0.65	4.17
5	C ₄ H ₈ Te(N ₃) ₂	3.62	3.28	0.34	4.42
6	C ₄ H ₈ Te(SeCN) ₂	3.77	3.02	0.75	-

Δ** = difference between (δ) -CH₂-Te- protons and (δ) -CH₂-C- protons

TABLE 2—¹H NMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS (δ) OF TETRAHALOTELLURACYCLOPENTANE ANIONIC COMPLEXES*

Sl. no	Compd./Complex	-CH ₂ -Te-(H')	-CH ₂ -C-(H')	Δ**	Others
1	C ₄ H ₈ TeI ₂	3.60 (m)	2.84 (m)	0.76	-
2	[(C ₂ H ₅) ₄ N] ₂ [C ₄ H ₈ TeI ₂ Cl ₂]	3.64 (m)	2.82 (m)	0.82	3.3 (q, CH ₂), 1.25 (t, CH ₃)
3	[(C ₂ H ₅) ₄ N] ₂ [C ₄ H ₈ TeI ₂ Br ₂]	3.65 (m)	2.84 (m)	0.81	3.3 (q, CH ₂), 1.25 (t, CH ₃)
4	[(C ₂ H ₅) ₄ N] ₂ [C ₄ H ₈ TeI ₂ I ₂]	3.66 (m)	2.84 (m)	0.82	3.3 (q, CH ₂), 1.18 (t, CH ₃)
5	[(C ₆ H ₅) ₄ P] ₂ [C ₄ H ₈ TeI ₂ Cl ₂]	3.67 (m)	2.84 (m)	0.83	-
6	[(C ₆ H ₅) ₄ P] ₂ [C ₄ H ₈ TeI ₂ Br ₂]	3.67 (m)	2.84 (m)	0.83	-
7	[(C ₆ H ₅) ₄ P] ₂ [C ₄ H ₈ TeI ₂ I ₂]	3.55 (m)	2.79 (m)	0.76	-
8	[(C ₆ H ₅) ₄ As] ₂ [C ₄ H ₈ TeI ₂ Cl ₂]	3.84 (m)	2.94 (m)	0.90	-
9	[(C ₆ H ₅) ₄ As] ₂ [C ₄ H ₈ TeI ₂ I ₂]	3.75 (m)	2.94 (m)	0.81	-
10	[(C ₆ H ₅) ₄ Sb] ₂ [C ₄ H ₈ TeI ₂ I ₂]	3.84 (m)	2.89 (m)	0.95	-

*Solvent CDCl₃, DMSO-d₆ for all compounds except sl. no. 2 (CDCl₃; spectra of all compounds at 90 MHz except sl. nos. 8-10 (60 MHz))

Δ** = explanation same as in Table 1

(++) = Broadening of peaks for -CH₂-Te-(H') and further splitting of each peak of -CH₂-C-(H') triplet, attributed to coupling of these protons with ¹⁴N of nuclear spin = 1

Electronegativity of X' (on Pauling scale): x_p of Cl, Br, I = 2.95, 2.62, 2.52 respectively.

Br, I) in Et_4N^+ complexes (sl. nos. 2–4) whereas such linearity is absent in Ph_4P^+ complexes particularly because of $(\text{Ph}_4\text{P})_2^{2+}$ ($\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{TeI}_2\text{I}_2$)²⁻ complex (sl. no. 7) and which may be attributed to the presence of π -interaction from electrons in the p -orbital of phosphorus atom and Te centre² and large size of iodine atom. The nonlinearity of (δ) - CH_2 -Te- and (δ) - CH_2 -C- protons in complexes (sl. nos. 7, 9, 10: Table 2) vs electronegativity of P, As, Sb is attributed to π -interaction between P and Te centre (sl. no. 7) and the absence or negligible contribution of such interaction in Ph_4As^+ and Ph_4Sb^+ complexes (sl. nos. 9, 10). Of all the complexes, in $(\text{Ph}_4\text{As})^+$ and $(\text{Ph}_4\text{Sb})^+$ complexes (sl. nos. 8–10) the multiplets corresponding to $-\text{CH}_2$ -Te- and $-\text{CH}_2$ -C- protons are best resolved and which may be attributed to the negligible interaction between $(\text{Ph}_4\text{As})^+$, $(\text{Ph}_4\text{Sb})^+$ cations and tetrahalotelluracyclopentane anions.

Experimental

All the complexes were synthesised by the exchange or additions of $\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{TeI}_2$ by reported methods¹ and gave

satisfactory elemental analyses. The integration of peak areas corresponded to the proposed stoichiometry (metal : ligand) of the complexes.

¹H nmr spectra ($\text{CDCl}_3/\text{CDCl}_3 + \text{DMSO-d}_6$) were recorded on Varian A60D and A90D spectrometers using TMS as internal reference.

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